

Code Switching used by Maudy Ayunda in Najwa Shihab YouTube Channel

Authors : Ni Wayan Widia Sri Meniang¹, Ni Luh Nyoman Seri Malini², Made Detriasmita Saientisna³, I Made Suastra⁴

Affiliations : ^{1,2,3,4} Udayana University

*Correspondence : niwayanwideasri@gmail.com

Abstract : This study was focused on an analysis of code-switching used by Maudy Ayunda found in the youtube video Catatan Najwa bersama Maudy Ayunda, which was hosted by Najwa Shihab. This study aimed to identify the types of code-switching and to know the reason for using code-switching by Maudy Ayunda. This research was classified as qualitative research with a descriptive method. The data of this study were collected by watching the video on Najwa Shihab's youtube channel and then analyzed descriptively. The theory used to analyze the types of code-switching is the code-switching theory by Hoffman (1991). According to Hoffman (1991), there are four types of code-switching: intra-sentential switching, inter-sentential switching, emblematic, and establishing continuity. The code-switching theory by Hoffman (1991) was also used to describe the reason for using code-switching. Hoffman (1991: 116) classified the reasons to use code-switching into seven points, namely, talking about a particular topic, quoting somebody else, being emphatic about something, interjection, repetition used for clarification, the intention of clarifying the speech content for the interlocutor and expressing group identity. As a result, in the conversation duration of 26 minutes, it was found that Maudy used the most inter-sentential switching, and the reason was talking about a particular topic.

Keywords : *Code-switching, types, reason, youtube video*

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1. Introduction

Language serves as a guide to social reality, it profoundly influences all of our thinking about social problems and processes, Sapir (1949). Today, over 7,100 languages are spoken around the world. Each of them contributes to the world's diversity and beauty. Because there are many languages worldwide, many people often speak two languages in one utterance without realizing it. People commonly use it to convey specific ideas that cannot be expressed in one language. It's all known as code-switching. This phenomenon can be observed not only in verbal communication but also in nonverbal communication on social media, Spolsky (in Imensiana, 2022).

Code-switching is defined by Hymes (in Waris, 2013) as the alternative employment of two or more languages, variations of language, or even speech styles. This topic is interesting to be discussed because easy to find the code-switching phenomenon, especially in Indonesia. Many Indonesian people learn foreign languages such as English, Korean, Japanese, or any other language, it can be seen from the number of foreign language courses notably English language in Indonesia. "Currently there are 18,999 courses from 70 types of skills. A total of 4,583 are English courses". Said Yusuf in Fox Business (Sulistiyoningrum, 2015).

In Indonesia, the phenomena of code-switching can be found in everyday life. Young people and public figures are the most likely to use code-switching. For example, in Indonesia, the phrase "kids jaman now" is common and popular because combining the languages makes it more impressive. Furthermore, this phenomenon can be found in real-life conversations and developed and easily accessible media such as television programs, social media, and YouTube channels. Unconsciously code-switching evolved and became more common in everyday life. Code-switching executes and resolves without disturbing its incident in its original context. It has been used by the speaker to operate or influence or describe the situation as desired, Sert (in Shafi et al., 2020)

This research discussed code-switching used by Maudy Ayunda in Catatan Najwa bersama Maudy Ayunda which is uploaded on Najwa Shihab's youtube channel. Maudy is one of the Indonesian artists who studied at Oxford University and graduated in 2016. In 2019, Maudy Ayunda continued her studies for a master's degree and was successfully accepted at two universities, they were Harvard University and Stanford University. In Najwa Shihab's YouTube video, Maudy shares her doubts about choosing Harvard University or Stanford University. In telling her story, Maudy Ayunda often unconsciously changes the language she uses from Indonesian to English. That is what we called Code-switching. This study will examine the types of code-switching that are used by Maudy Ayunda on Najwa Shihab's youtube channel. The aim is to find the type of code-switching used by Maudy Ayunda and to describe the reasons behind the use of code-switching by Maudy Ayunda when talking to Najwa Shihab.

This study was inspired by a previous study that have a similar topic with this study. One of them was Linuwih & Kartika (2018) which analyzed Code Switching and Code Mixing Used by Sarah Sechan and Cinta Laura in Sarah Sechan Talk Show. The previous study was more focused on observing the use of Indonesian-English code switching and code mixing used by Sarah Sechan as a host and Cinta Laura as a guest in Sarah Sechan's talk show. There were 3 code-switching found in the previous study, 3 code-mixing, and 6 reasons used by Cinta Laura and Sarah Sechan. The results of this study indicate that Sarah Sechan uses intra-sentential code-switching more often, the reason being to express her feeling and emotions

(interjection). On the other hand, Cinta Laura uses intra-sentential switching more often to talk about her bio, career, and job (expressing group). Due to my observation, this thesis well discussed code-switching used by Cinta Laura and Sarah Sechan, but the current study analyzed codeswitching used by Maudy Ayunda by using the code-switching theory by Hoffman (1991).

The use of code-switching in one of the Indonesian movies, *Twivortiere* was analyzed by Dira & Lazar (2019). A qualitative method was used in this study and data was taken from the conversation between the characters in the *Twivortare* film transcript. The results of this study found that the characters in this film utilize all of the three categories of code-switching as intra-sentential, inter-sentential, and tag-switching in their conversation, especially when using daily language. Due to my observation, this thesis well discussed code-switching found in film but the current study analyzed code-switching used by Maudy Ayunda on the youtube channel Najwa Shihab by using the code-switching theory by Hoffman (1991).

Code-switching in one of the social media types namely WhatsApp was also analyzed by Atriasih & Jayantini (2022). This previous study identified the types and the function of code-switching on the Universitas Mahasaraswati Denpasar's researchers' WhatsApp group. The data were taken from the researchers' WhatsApp group. This previous study focused to analyze the types and functions of code-switching in WhatsApp groups. As a result, the types of 15 data texts were intra-sentential switching. Based on the chosen theory, the expressive function was the most commonly used function of code-switching. Due to my observation, this journal well discussed code-switching found in one social media but the current study analyzed code-switching used by Maudy Ayunda on the youtube channel Najwa Shihab by using code-switching theory by Hoffman (1991).

Code-switching in one of the Youtube channels was also analyzed by Imensiana (2022). The data was taken from Naila Farhana's youtube channel and analyzed using the code-switching theory by Poplack (1980) and Gumperz (1982). This study described the types and functions of code-switching used by Naila Farhana. As a result, from the three types of code-switching, the dominant used is intra-sentential switching, and the most dominant function found was message qualification used by Naila Farhana utterances. Due to my observation, this thesis well discussed code-switching found in Naila's youtube channel but it was focused to found the types and functions of codeswitching in Naila's utterances the current study analyzed code-switching used by Maudy Ayunda on the youtube channel Najwa Shihab by using code-switching theory by Hoffman (1991) and focused to found types and reason of code-switching used by Maudy Ayunda.

2. Method

This research was classified as qualitative research with a descriptive method to explain a fact from a phenomenon. The data was taken from Najwa Shihab's YouTube channel. YouTube is a video-sharing website in the digital world, (Afryanti et al., 2021) The data was chosen because of the large number of code-switching found during the conversation between the host and the guest. This research focuses on analyzing the types of code-switching and the reasons for using code-switching in this YouTube video. The method of collecting data was watching and listening to dialogues and note-taking an important point. The note-taking technique is the practice of recording information from different sources by writing down the data needed (Creswell, 2009). The collected data were analyzed using the theory of code-switching by Hoffman 1991. In the end, the results were presented in a descriptive method of

presenting data analysis which began with the data then the results were analyzed using the selected theory.

3. Result and Discussion

According to Hoffman (1991), four types of code-switching exist based on the juncture or scope of switching where the language occurs: intra-sentential switching, inter-sentential switching, emblematic switching, and establishing continuity. In this section, an analysis of the use of code-switching on the YouTube video of Catatan Najwa bersama Maudy Ayunda was analyzed. In the video, Najwa Shihab as the host asked a few things about Maudy's education which focuses more on Maudy's confusion about choosing Stanford or Harvard as a place to continue her master's degree. Maudy Ayunda used four different types of code-switching in Catatan Najwa Bersama Maudy:

- **Intra-Sentential Switching**

Code-switching within a clause or sentence is referred to as intra-sentential. In this case, speakers can substitute clause fragments, lexical items, or even morphemes, Hoffman (1991). Here is the intra-sentential switching used by Maudy Ayunda in Catatan Najwa Bersama Maudy:

Data 1

Intra-sentential switching in Maudy's utterance (05.19-05.31)

*"Sempet baca kaya dikirimin temen, dikirimin bude pakde gitu di **group family** gitu. Terus akhirnya... **search** deh **search** deh gitu, trus aku search di twitter ya ampun lucu-lucu banget".*

(I read it like, it was sent by a friend, it was sent by Buk de Pak de in a family group. It's like..search it, so I did a search on Twitter, oh my goodness, it was really funny).

In this data, Najwa Shihab and Maudy talked about the viral news about Maudy Ayunda. Maudy conveys her reaction to the hashtag on Twitter that mention her name. At first, Maudy spoke in Indonesian language but sometimes she switches her language to English. The changes of language in Maudy's utterance were considered Intra-sentential switching. It can be seen in the words 'group family' and 'search'. She prefers to use English words to mention group family and search because they are familiar and widely used in her country.

According to Hoffman (1991), there are seven reasons why people use code-switching, they are talking about a particular topic, quoting somebody else, being emphatic about something, interjection, repetition used for clarification, the intention of clarifying the speech content for the interlocutor, and expressing group identity. The reason for using code-switching Maudy was talking about a particular topic. According to Holmes (1992), people may switch the code during a speech event to discuss a specific topic. As mentioned above, Maudy gives her reaction about the particular topic which is the viral hashtag on Twitter about her. She felt comfortable the word search in English rather than cari or telusuri in Indonesia because people commonly say the word search when they talk about something viral on Twitter.

Data 2

Intra-sentential switching in Maudy's utterance (17.51-18.00)

*“Yang kedua juga memang orang tua aku apa ya, kalo dari obrolan mereka itu **the reward** dari **achievement** itu kayak perasaan bangga aja kita gapernah dikasi **incentive** kayak uang atau jajanan atau apa sih”.*

(The second is also my parents like, from their conversation, the reward for achievement is like feeling proud. We have never been given incentives like money or snacks or anything).

In this data, Najwa Shihab and Maudy talked about Maudy's experience of how her parents treated her. At first, Maudy spoke in Indonesian language but sometimes she switched her language to English. It can be seen in the word "reward, achievement, and incentive". She prefers to use those words in English because they are familiar and commonly used by bilingual people. According to the seven types of using code-switching by Hoffman, the reason behind the use of code-switching is the intention of clarifying the speech content for the interlocutor. Code-switching will often occur when a bilingual speaks with another bilingual so that the speech can be understood by one another, Hoffman (1991). As mentioned above, Maudy told Najwa Shihab about how her parents treated her, in the example above Maudy used code switching in mentioning rewards, achievements, and incentives when she talked with Najwa as a bilingual speaker too.

• Inter-sentential Switching

Code-switching that occurs between clause or sentence boundaries is referred to as inter-sentential. In this case, the entire clause or sentence is in one language, but the next clause or sentence is in another language. Here is the inter-sentential switching used by Maudy Ayunda in Catatan Najwa Bersama Maudy:

Data 1

Inter-sentential Switching in Maudy's utterance (10.38-10.48)

*“Akhirnya aku merasa ini yang paling bikin aku waktu nulis agak pengen nangis **and like my friend told me that's the one, if that's the one that closes to you**”.*

(Finally, I feel that this is what makes me the most when I write I want to cry, and like my friend told me that's the one if that's the one that is close to you).

In this data, Najwa Shihab read one of the netizen's questions for Maudy Ayunda about the motivation letter. Maudy expressed her experience in writing a motivation letter and her friend help her to correct hers. In the example above clearly seen that Maudy switched her language sentence by sentence at the end she spoke English to repeat what her friend said to her. The changes of language in Maudy's utterance were considered inter-sentential switching. It can be seen from the sentence "And like my friend told me that's the one, if that's the one that closes to you" She prefers to use the English language to explain her experience. According to Hoffman (1991), there are seven reasons why people use code-switching, they are talking about a particular topic, quoting somebody else, being emphatic about something, interjection, repetition used for clarification, the intention of clarifying the speech content for the interlocutor, and expressing group identity. The reason for using code-switching Maudy was talking about a particular topic. People may switch codes during a

speech event to discuss a specific topic, Holmes (1992). As mentioned above, Maudy expressed her experience and also her friend's comment about her about the particular topic which was her motivation letter.

Data 2

Inter-sentential Switching in Maudy's utterance (25.07-25.15)

*"Aku langsung merasa kayak **you know this is a privilege, this is something that I'm lucky to have**".*

(I immediately felt like you know this is a privilege, this is something that I am lucky to have).

In this data, Najwa Shihab asked Maudy Ayunda about her feeling after achieving her dream. Maudy conveyed her opinion about what she felt after achieving her dream. Maudy express her experience in writing a motivation letter and her friend help her to correct hers. In the example above clearly seen that Maudy switch her language sentence by sentence at the end she used English to convey her feeling. The changes of language in Maudy's utterance were considered inter-sentential switching. It can be seen from the sentence "You know this is a privilege, this is something that I'm lucky to have". She preferred to use the English language to explain her feeling after using the Indonesian language at first. According to the seven types of using code-switching by Hoffman, the reason behind the use of code-switching was emphatic about something. When a person talks a language other than his/her mother tongue suddenly, they want to empathize or even assert something. In the example above, Maudy expressed her feeling by saying "lucky to have (opportunity)" and asserting that was a privilege.

Data 3

Inter-sentential Switching in Maudy's utterance (20.40-20.47)

*"Temen temen harus tau aku **bener bener ngerasa aku ga akan keterima maksudnya kayak aku honestly felt like I was beating the odds**".*

(Guys, you should know that I really feel like I won't be accepted, I mean, I honestly felt like I was beating the odds).

In this data, Najwa Shihab asked Maudy Ayunda about her feeling in the process to achieve her dream. Then Maudy conveys her experience about what she felt in the process to achieve her dream. In the example above clearly seen that Maudy switch her language sentence by sentence at the end she used English to convey her feeling. The changes of language in Maudy's utterance were considered inter-sentential switching. It can be seen from the sentence "honestly felt like I was beating the odds" She preferred to use the English language to explain her feeling after using the Indonesian language at first. According to the seven types of using code-switching by Hoffman, the reason behind the use of code-switching was repetition used for clarification. Repetition is the reason in which the speaker wants to clarify their statement. It will be better understood by listeners, sometimes people can use a second language that they speak to say the same thing. In this case, Maudy explained her thoughts in Indonesia first, then explain them once more in English.

- **Emblematic**

Emblematic occurs when someone inserts a tag from one language into the utterance of another language to emphasize something. Here is the emblematic that used by Maudy Ayunda in Catatan Najwa Bersama Maudy:

Data 1

Emblematic in Maudy's utterance (11.25-11.36)

Najwa: *Padahal baru awal masuk, can you imagine the inside?*

(Even though it's just the beginning, can you imagine the inside?)

Maudy: ***Exactly**, makanya itu juga yang bikin aku gila sih standford aja dari sisi applicationnya makes me growth rom the process gitu.*

(Exactly, that's what makes me think wow Stanford's application side makes me grow from the process like that).

In this data, Najwa Shihab asked Maudy Ayunda has she imagined the inside of Stanford. Then Maudy conveys her opinion about it. Maudy gave a response to Najwa's statement. In the example above clearly seen that Maudy wanted to emphasize her opinion by adding the tag "exactly". It was regarded as emblematic because it entails the insertion of a tag, interjection, or sentence filler in the other language that serves as an ethnic identity marker. According to the seven types of using code-switching by Hoffman, the reason behind the use of code-switching was an interjection. An interjection is also used when someone wants to react with an excited atmosphere or feel surprised. In the conversation above can be seen that Maudy feels so excited and surprised in replying to Najwa's statement by saying "Exactly".

- **Establishing continuity**

Establishing continuity occurs when an Indonesian speaker speaks in English and then another speaker responds in English as well. Here is the establishing continuity used by Maudy Ayunda in Catatan Najwa Bersama Maudy:

Data 1

Establishing continuity in Maudy's utterance (23.35-23.37)

Najwa: *Yaa you enjoying the process?*

(Yes, you enjoying the process?)

Maudy: *Yaa we're **enjoying the process** gitu*

(Yes, I enjoying the process like that)

In this data, Najwa Shihab asked Maudy Ayunda about her relationship with her boyfriend. Then Maudy answer it, at the end of the conversation, Najwa asked one more time by saying "Yaa, you enjoying the process?". Maudy gave a respond to Najwa's statement Maudy by saying the same things as Najwa. In the example above clearly seen that Maudy repeats the same sentence as Najwa then is considered as establishing continuity. According to the seven types of using code-switching by Hoffman, the reason behind the use of code-switching was talking about a particular topic. In the conversation above can be seen that

Maudy and Najwa talk about a particular topic which was her relationship process with her boyfriend.

4. Conclusion

Based on the data analysis the result of this study is found that Maudy Ayunda always uses code-switching to do conversations with Najwa Shihab. Both Najwa Shihab and Mudy Ayunda were bilingual speakers. Code-switching is often found when a bilingual speaker has a conversation with another bilingual speaker so speech can be understood by one another. In answering Najwa Shihab's questions and statements, Maudy used four types of code-switching such as intra-sentential switching, inter-sentential switching, emblematic, and establishing continuity. However, inter-sentential switching is more dominant than the other types. Maudy has several reasons for using code-switching, but the most dominant reason is talking about a particular topic. Even though code-switching happened many times, the conversation was held smoothly because Najwa Shihab, as the host, was also fluent in English. Since code-switching is popular in this era, future researcher can develop their research to analyze code-switching by comparing the use of English and other languages in a conversation.

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